

AN ASSESSMENT OF TOURISTS' CHARACTERISTICS TOWARD GREEN PRACTICES IN TOURISM

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Abstract

From the tension of climate change, green practices in tourism have emerged. Green practices in tourism are the steps to minimize environmental contamination to protect the environment. By this study, the researcher tries to measure the tourists' characteristics towards green practices conducted in 2018. With addressing the basic objective of examining the agreement of the tourists to green tourism practices the study also finds the awareness of green practices, views of the tourist about the chance of such practices in the time of the tour, and the consequences of the test of the association between green practices and their characteristics. The tourist visiting Cox's Bazar is the population of the study from where 143 are drawn as sample adopting simple random sampling technique and then interviews are taken by personal interview. Chi-square test (χ^2) is used to test the association. The test explores that there is a significant association of green practices with the level of education and monthly income of the tourists. Other characteristics have no significant association with green practices.

Keywords: Tourism, Green Practices

Introduction

In present-day tourism is the most important international economic force in the 21st century. It is considered as a growing business and the peak industry all over the world. UNCTAD (2007) identifies tourism as the largest and fastest rising industry in the world. Nowadays tourism is the most beneficial and modern business throughout the world (Tuhin & Mojumdar, 2011). As a main worldwide economic force tourism contributes currently about 7 percent of the global export of goods and services (TRIP Consultants, 2007). Like other developing countries in the globe tourism has turned out to be a significant sector for economic escalation in Bangladesh (Islam, 2009). Over the world, Bangladesh is one of the

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mainly visited vacationer destinations. The unique aspects of the diversity of tourist destinations of this country are to please the most travelers. So, the tourism industry of Bangladesh is gaining international attention in the course of time. Industrial Policy of 1999 in Bangladesh has included tourism as an industry. It also identified this industry as a 'Thrust Sector' bearing in mind its stable growth and sustainable development. Tourism's contribution to poverty alleviation has been recognized by the National Tourism Policy 1992 (Bangladesh Tourism Vision 2020, 2006). But today the tourism industry is criticized by the environmental-conscious people all over the world. Historically, the concern for the environment was referred to as industries responsible for direct contamination through their harmful activities. However, the rising awareness of the impact of daily human actions on the natural environment has led to the recognition that all individuals and businesses should be engaged in reducing environmental pollution and resource consumption, and the tourism industry is not exempt from this obligation. According to Sloan, Legrand, and Chen (Sloan, Legrand & Chen, 2009), stockholders, employees and customers have increasing expectations of the tourism and hospitality industry to be economically, socially, and environmentally responsible. To keep away from the brand impact of negativity, the tourism sector requires to thinking green consciousness in their product deliverance and telling guests about it. It is significantly important to redecorate the general perspective and actions about environmental matters and tourism. If not, no safety tourism possibility in the future will remain. In recent years, tourists are becoming demanding green tourism avoiding destinations with a bad environment. Increased consciousness of the people and tourists now has made several questions of tourism activities against the environment which leads the tourism business to be caring for the environment. As a result, the term *green practice* in tourism has evolved in the tourism sector. Green practices in tourism include several actions by the diverse with tourists' stakeholders of the tourism industry that confirm the lessen pollution of the environment. Tourism business organizations are trying to adapt to this situation over the world that makes a path to go ahead to be green. The deepest thought is here whether tourists have the agreement to green practices? What is the status of the tourists' characteristics (socioeconomic and demographic) in green practices in tourism? To find the answers to these questions, the psychological involvement of the tourists must be measured toward the green matter of tourism.

Statement of the Research Problem

From the above discussion, it is clear that today green practices by the tourists are immensely important because of the change of climate and environmental pollution. To compete with the global competitor tourism industry must take the green factors in considerations with importance. For the business people, understanding and analyzing the attitudes of travelers toward green tourism practices is a matter of concentration at this moment to measure the potentials of such green tourism in Bangladesh. Hence, the pertinent question of this research is: Do travelers support green practices in tourism? Appropriate

answers to the question lie on the assessment of the agreement of tourists toward green practices in tourism.

Objectives of the Study

The basic objective of the study, from a broad perspective, is to examine the agreement of the tourists to green tourism practices. Specific objectives are to—

- a) Measure the awareness of the tourists toward green practices in tourism.
- b) Know the view of the tourists about if there is any chance to exercise green at the time of the tour.
- c) Assess the agreement of the tourists to green practices against their socioeconomic and demographic characteristics.

Literature Review

Amin (2007) shows the contribution of tourism in the world economy. He identifies tourism as one of the largest industries in the globe which is contributing over ten percent (10%) to global GDP. Economically, this industry creates jobs and contributes to a country's GDP bringing in capital investment and exports.

At present tourism is a global industry making the involvement of hundreds of millions of people in domestic with international travel each year (Mason, 2003).

According to Rahman (2007), the tourism industry of Bangladesh has vast potentials from the sense of foreign exchange earner and provider of job opportunities. It has the resulting multiplier effect on the country's economy altogether.

Weather and climate have brought significance for tourist decision-making and the travel experience. Both at home and destinations, the climate is the most important motivator in tourism. Either consciously or by implicitly climate is considered by tourists during tour planning (Scott, Hall, Gosling, 2012).

According to UNEP Manuals on Sustainable Tourism (UNEP Manuals, 2008), tourism is considered as an extremely climate-sensitive economic segment for its close relations to the environment and climate. In UNEP Manuals on Sustainable Tourism 2008, it is reported that Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the most significant greenhouse gas accounting for an estimated 60% of the warming.

A report by UNWTO-UNEP-WMO (2008) expresses that emissions from tourism activities contribute about 5% of worldwide CO₂ emissions. Additional greenhouse gases as well create important contributions to worldwide temperature. Tourism's contribution to

worldwide warming was estimated for the year 2005. It was found that its contribution was between 5% and 14% to the overall warming caused by human being emissions of greenhouse gases¹. In his discussion on the contribution of the environment to the degradation by tourism, Glem Kreag (2001) explores the generation of the different types of waste and contamination by the tourists.

Destinations that define themselves as ‘*Going Green*’ adopt and express environmentally friendly practices, while apparently small, can make a big distinction when added up. The desire to be thoughtful of the impact of the industry on the environment is there (Compass Insights into Tourism Branding, 2010).

Through the adoption of green practices by a growing number of hotels, the hospitality industry is making changes in the interests of their customers. A few smaller upscale hotels are getting 15-20% of their business coming because of their green attempts (Natz, 2008). It is obvious that green tourism can offer different benefits as broad economic, social and environmental benefits for the host countries as well as their communities (Mill and Morrison, 2006). Though not important now, it is probable that decision making related to climate will start to influence tourism markets in the future either for tourists’ awareness on their personal carbon foot (Simmons & Becken, 2004), or for negative changes at destinations.

One-third to one half of international tourists (weighted toward the USA) surveyed in a study said if companies benefit local communities and conservation, they were ready to pay more (CESD and TIES, 2005).

Lin and Huang (2012) claim that consumers who have a high level of environmental concern stimulate the tendency for environmental-friendly products and they willingly choose them in purchasing. There are several studies explored the relationship between green hotel choices and subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, green consumption, or daily environmental behavior (Han et al., 2009, 2010; Han, Hsu, Lee, & Sheu, 2011; Kim & Han, 2010; Lee et al., 2010; Tsai & Tsai, 2008).

Review of related literatures from the previous couple of years express that the researches on tourism and green tourism focus on contributions and status of tourism (Amin, 2007; Mason, 2003; & Rahman, 2007), influence of climate change in decision making of tourism (Daniel Scott, Colin Michael Hall & Stefan Gossling, 2012; Lin & Huang 2012; Han et al.,

¹ UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme) Manuals on Sustainable Tourism (2008), Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation in the Tourism Sector: Frameworks, Tools and Practices, p. 15

2009, 2010; Han, Hsu, Lee, & Sheu, 2011; Kim & Han, 2010; Lee et al., 2010; Tsai & Tsai, 2008), how tourism is affected by climate change (UNEP Manuals on Sustainable Tourism, 2008 & Natz, 2008), the environment is polluted by how and whom from the tourism industry (Glem Kreg, 2001), evolution of green tourism and development of green practices in tourism (Compass Insights into Tourism Branding, 2010), and benefits of green practices in tourism (Mill & Morrison, 2006; World Economic Forum 2009; Klytchnikova & Dorosh, 2009 & TIES 2005). Pieces of literature provide the evidence that no research was performed emphasizing the agreement to green practices of the tourists which can ensure the real green tourism. By conducting this study, this vital research gap is satisfied.

Methodology of the Study

Population, Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Sampling is the process of selecting a few (a sample) from a bigger group (the sampling population) to become the basis for estimating or predicting the prevalence of an unknown piece of information, situation or outcome regarding the bigger group and a sample is a subgroup of the population (Kumar, 2005). In sampling design, the researcher includes defining the population, deciding sampling technique and determination of sample size. The population is the whole people, events, or things of interest that the researcher wants to investigate (Sekaran, 2006). The population for the study includes tourists visiting Cox's Bazar. Tourists from various hotels and restaurants are drawn by using a simple random sampling method. Gay and Airasian (2003) define random sampling as the method where each respondent has an equal chance to be chosen for the study. In an attempt to measure the agreement of tourists to green practices, a total number of 143 respondents are selected. Through applying the following formula and calculation the sample size is taken.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Sample size } (n_0) &= \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2} \\ &= \frac{(1.64)^2 (0.5)(0.5)}{(0.07)^2} \\ &= 138 \text{ (approximately)}\end{aligned}$$

Where:

n_0 = desired sample size.

Z^2 = standard normal deviate set at 1.64, which corresponds to the 90% confidence level.

p = assumed proportion in the target population estimated to have a particular characteristics.

d = allowable maximum error in estimating population proportion.

Data Collection: Tools, Techniques and Quality Check

For the study, data are collected by conducting the field interview. The survey method is followed to assemble primary data. The survey method of obtaining information is based on the questioning of respondents (Malhotra, 2001). The study is done based on the sample survey. A sample survey is defined as a method of gathering primary data based on communication with a representative sample of individuals (Islam, 2016). Surveys are completed by a pre-set questionnaire that contains structured questions. Structured questions specify the set of response alternatives and the response format (Malhotra, 2001). The questionnaire holds scale and dichotomous questions. Some open-ended questions, especially for obtaining identification information, are included in the questionnaire. For the study the researcher checks the quality of data by repeating questions, probing and applying statistical tools.

Data Management and Analysis

To draw the findings of the study in analyzing data the researcher has addressed data preparation and exploring, examining, and rearranging data for finding out the meaningful descriptions. Editing of data is a process of examining the collected raw data (especially, in surveys) to detect errors and omissions and to correct these when possible. Editing is done to assure that the data are accurate, consistent with other facts gathered, uniformly entered, as completed as possible and have been well arranged to facilitate coding and tabulation (Kothari & Garg, 2014). After collecting the data from the respondents under this study to identify errors and omissions, make rectifications whenever possible, and certify that minimum data quality standards are achieved, the researcher takes the step of editing the data. Editing of data is accomplished by in-house editing where the questionnaire undergoes thorough editing. Numerical coding is incorporated for the study. Pre-coding is applied in the questionnaire. After collecting, the researcher starts to enter the coded information into a file directly from the questionnaire. The prepared file is stored on a pen drive. Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) 21.0 is made use of. To draw results of the study data are analyzed by the graphical model. A graphical model is visual and is used to isolate variables and to suggest directions of the relationship but is not designed to provide numerical results (Malhotra, 2001).

Data Analysis

Socioeconomic and Demographic Characteristics

The table (table-1) on the next page shows the different socioeconomic and demographic data of the tourists. Gender and age of the respondents, their marital status, level of education of the interviewees, occupation, and their monthly income are presented in the table and also discussed below.

Table 1: The socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Sub-variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	114	80
	Female	29	20
	Total	143	100
Age of the respondent (Years)	18 – 30	49	35
	31 – 40	53	37
	41 - 50	32	22
	51 - 60	6	4
	61 - 70	3	2
	Total	143	100
Marital Status	Married	104	73
	Single	39	27
	Total	143	100
Level of education	Primary	16	11
	Secondary School Certificate (SSC)	16	11
	Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC)	23	16
	Graduate	45	32
	Post Graduate	43	30
	Total	143	100
Occupation	Students	15	11
	Self-employed	39	27
	Professional (Teaching, Doctor and Engineering)	27	19
	Manager/Executive	25	17
	Government Officer	27	19
	Unemployed	10	7
	Total	143	100
Monthly income (taka in thousands)	No income	20	14
	Less than 30	13	9
	30 – 40	31	22
	41 – 50	28	20
	51 - 60	26	18
	More than 60	25	17
	Total	143	100

Table-1 reveals that among the respondents 80% is male and the remaining 20% of them are female. In the question of age among them 37% of respondents are in the range of 31 to 40 years old, 35% are under the range of 18 to 30 years old, and 22% have the age under the range of 41 to 50 years old. It is also clear from the table that 73% of the respondents are married and the rest of them are single. In terms of the level of education, 32% of respondents are graduates, 30% are post-graduate, 16% are HSC-pass, 11% are SSC-pass and the remaining 11% is from primary education. In the question of occupation, it is seen from the table that 27% of the respondents are self-employed, 19% are professional, 19% are government officers, 17% are managers/executives, 11% are students and the remaining 7% are unemployed. Monthly income (in thousands taka) is presented in the socio-demographic table. The table demonstrates that 14% of the respondents have no income, 18% have income in the range of 51 to 60 thousand, 17% earn more than 60 thousand taka, 22% have the income of 30 to 40 thousand, 20% of respondents' income is in the range of 41 to 50 thousand and 9% respondents earn less than 30 thousand taka.

Awareness about Green Practices to the Tourists

The researcher assesses whether tourists have awareness about green practices in tourism. The following chart (chart-1) shows the result before the question of 'Do you know about green practices in tourism?' It is clear from the illustration-1 that among the sample tourists only 26% has the familiarity with green practices in tourism and most of the tourists (74%) have no idea about such practices.

Awareness of green tourism practices
(Do you know about green practices in tourism?)

Fig. 1: Awareness about green practices in tourism

Chance to Exercise Green

The researcher takes the step to know the view of the sample tourists about if there is any chance to exercise green in the time of the tour. The responses are distributed in the following table (Table 2). Table 2 expresses that among the tourists 17% think that a tourist can get the option to exercise and 12% thought is negative on such an issue. Most of the tourists (71%) are confused about whether there is any possibility to exercise green in the time of the tour.

Table 2: Distribution of responses regarding the chance of green practices

Responses	Whether there is any chance to exercise green in the time of tour	
	Number	Percent (%)
Yes	24	17
No	18	12
Don't know	101	71
Total	143	100

Assessment of Agreement of the Respondents to Green Practices

From Table 3, it is seen that among 57 tourists 78.9% of *male* respondents agree that *Green Practice should be followed by them* and 21.1% of *female* respondents provide the same answer. From the 65 travelers, 76.9% of *male* respondents are strongly agreed on such a problem whereas 23.1% of the *female* is strongly agreed on such an issue. 100% (among 3) of *male* interviewees are strongly disagreed that *Green practice should be followed*. In the case of disagreement 16 respondents are disagreed where 87.5% is from the *male* and 12.5% is from *female* respondents.

Table 3: Green practice by gender

		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Green practice	Strongly disagree	3 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)
	Disagree	14 (87.5%)	2 (12.5%)	16 (100.0%)
	Neither agree nor disagree	2 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0%)
	Agree	45 (78.9%)	12 (21.1%)	57 (100.0%)
	Strongly agree	50 (76.9%)	15 (23.1%)	65 (100.0%)
Total		114 (79.7%)	29 (20.3%)	143(100.0%)

Type of test $\chi^2 = 2.207$, df = 4, p-value = .698

The association between *Green Practice* and *Gender* is statistically tested and found to be insignificant.

The following table (Table 4) shows that 67.70%, respondents are from the range of *18 to 40 years old* and 32.3% of respondents, who are in the range of *41 to 70 years old*, are strongly agreed about *Green Practice* where the total number of the respondents is 65. Among 57 respondents who are agreed about *Green Practice*, 71.9% have the age of *18 to 40 years old* and 28.1% are under the range of *41 to 70 years old*. In case of disagreement, 81.2% of respondents of age *18 to 40 years old* and 18.8% are from the range of *41 to 70 years old* from the total number of 16. Only three (3) respondents are strongly disagreed on such an issue where the table demonstrates that 66.7% of respondents are under the range of *18 to 40 years old* and 33.3% are under the range of *41 to 70 years old*.

Table 4: Green practice by age

		Age		Total
		18 to 40 years	41 to 70 years	
Green practice	Strongly disagree	2 (66.7%)	1 (33.3%)	3 (100.0%)
	Disagree	13 (81.2%)	3 (18.8%)	16 (100.0%)
	Neither agree nor disagree	2 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0%)
	Agree	41 (71.9%)	16 (28.1%)	57 (100.0%)
	Strongly agree	44 (67.7%)	21 (32.3%)	65 (100.0%)
Total		102 (71.3%)	41 (28.7%)	143 (100.0%)

Type of test $\chi^2 = 2.036$, df = 4, p-value = .729

Table 5, shows that among the 57 respondents 35.1%, who are *single*, is agreed on *Green Practice* and 64.9% of *married* respondents are agreed on such issues in their personal life. 76.9% *married* individual (tourist) is strongly agreed and 23.1% *single-respondent* are strongly agreed, from the total number of 65 tourists, about *Green Practice*. On the other hand, only three (3) respondents are strongly disagreed, 66.7% are *married* and 33.3% are *single*, about *Green Practice*. 81.2% of *married* and 18.8% of *single* respondents, among 16 interviewees, is disagreed.

There is no statistically significant association between *Green Practice* and *Marital Status*; that is, both *Single* and *Married* equally give their responses on *Green Practice*.

From Table 6, it is found that there are 65 tourists who are strongly agreed on Green Practice wherein 75.4% of respondents are from the level of higher education and 24.6% is from the level of *primary to mid education*. The table also provides evidence that among 57 respondents 56.1% from the *higher education* and 43.9% from the *primary to mid education* are agreed on the issue. 16 respondents where 62.5% contains the *primary to mid* and 37.5% who have a *higher education* have disagreed for *Green Practice*.

Table 5: Green practice by marital status

		Marital status		Total
		Single	Married	
Green practice	Strongly disagree	1 (33.3%)	2 (66.7%)	3 (100.0%)
	Disagree	3 (18.8%)	13 (81.2%)	16 (100.0%)
	Neither agree nor disagree	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0%)	2 (100.0%)
	Agree	20 (35.1%)	37 (64.9%)	57 (100.0%)
	Strongly agree	15 (23.1%)	50 (76.9%)	65 (100.0%)
Total		39 (27.3%)	104 (72.7%)	143 (100.0%)

Type of test $\chi^2 = 3.724$, df = 4, p-value = .445

Table 6: Green practice by level of education

		Level of education		Total
		Primary-mid (Primary, SSC and HSC)	Higher education (Graduate and Postgraduate)	
Green practice	Strongly disagree	3 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)
	Disagree	10 (62.5%)	6 (37.5%)	16 (100.0%)
	Neither agree nor disagree	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	2 (100.0%)
	Agree	25 (43.9%)	32 (56.1%)	57 (100.0%)
	Strongly agree	16 (24.6%)	49 (75.4%)	65 (100.0%)
Total		55 (38.5%)	88 (61.5%)	143 (100.0%)

Type of test $\chi^2 = 14.786$, df = 4, p-value = .005

The association between *Green Practice* and *Level of Education* is found statistically to be significant.

Phi and Cramer's V are both tests of the strength of association. We can see that (from table-7) the strength of the association between the variables is somewhat strong.

Table 7: Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.322	.005
	Cramer's V	.322	.005
N of Valid Cases		143	

It is obvious from the table (table-8) that among the respondents 65 are strongly agreed with different occupations about Green Practice. 24.6% of professionals, 23.1% government officer, 21.5% self-employed, 16.9% manager/executive, 9.2% student and 4.6% unemployed respondents are strongly agreed on such issue. Among the 57 respondents 26.3% self-employed, 19.3% manager/executive, 19.3% government officer, 15.8% professionals, 10.5% student, and 8.8% unemployed are agreed about Green Practice.

Table 8: Green practice by occupation

		Occupation						Total
		Student	Self-employed	Professional (Teacher, Doctor and Engineer)	Manager /Executive	Government officer	Unemployed	
Green practice	Strongly disagree	0 0.0%	2 66.7%	0 0.0%	1 33.3%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	3 100.0%
	Disagree	2 12.5%	8 50.0%	1 6.2%	2 12.5%	2 12.5%	1 6.2%	16 100.0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 50.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 50.0%	2 100.0%
	Agree	6 10.5%	15 26.3%	9 15.8%	11 19.3%	11 19.3%	5 8.8%	57 100.0%
	Strongly agree	6 9.2%	14 21.5%	16 24.6%	11 16.9%	15 23.1%	3 4.6%	65 100.0%
Total		14 9.8%	39 27.3%	27 18.9%	25 17.5%	28 19.6%	10 7.0%	143 100.0%

Type of test $\chi^2 = 20.332$, df = 20, p-value = .437

The association between *Green Practice* and *Occupation* is statistically tested and found to be insignificant.

It is found from the table-9 that among 65 respondents 55.4% have a *monthly income of more than taka 50,000* are strongly agreed about *Green Practice*. On this issue 30.8% of respondents whose *monthly income is taka 30,000 to 50,000* are strongly agreed, 12.3% of respondents are also strongly agreed who have *no income*. 57 respondents are agreed about *Green Practice* where the distribution is 52.6% from the *monthly level of income of taka 30,000 to 50,000*, 19.3% from the *monthly income level of more than taka 50,000*, 15.8% who have *no income*, and 12.3% whose *monthly income is less than taka 30,000*. In a question of disagreement, 43.8% of respondents who have *monthly income range is taka 30,000 to 50,000* among 16 respondents are have disagreed. The association between *Green Practice* and *Monthly income* is statistically tested and found to be highly significant.

Table 9: Green practice by monthly income

		Monthly income (in taka)				Total
		Less than 30,000	30,000 to 50,000	More than 50,000	No income	
Green Practice	Strongly disagree	0 (0.0%)	2 (66.7%)	1 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)
	Disagree	3 (18.8%)	7 (43.8%)	3 (18.8%)	3 (18.8%)	16 (100.0%)
	Neither agree nor disagree	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0%)
	Agree	7 (12.3%)	30 (52.6%)	11 (19.3%)	9 (15.8%)	57 (100.0%)
	Strongly agree	1 (1.5%)	20 (30.8%)	36 (55.4%)	8 (12.3%)	65 (100.0%)
Total		12 (8.4%)	60 (42.0%)	51 (35.7%)	20 (14.0%)	143 (100.0%)

Type of test $\chi^2 = 29.648$, df = 12, p-value = .003

Findings and Interpretations

Certainly, it carries significance to recognize the degree of awareness of the tourists about green practices in tourism in the study before investing sufficient efforts to test the association between green practices and their own characteristics which is done effectively. Also, the view of them about the chance of such practices in the time of their tour should be

and is measured by the researcher. The next two statements communicate the consequences of those twin actions. The result before the question on whether tourists have the awareness about green practices in tourism explains that the majority of them have no familiarity with that issue. 74% of the respondents have no idea about green practices in tourism. Also, the study explores that most of the tourists are confused about whether there is any chance to exercise green at the time of the tour. A minimum number of tourists think that there are some options to work out green tourism is greater than the negative thought of the tourists on such issues. The involvement of the characteristics of the tourists (socioeconomic and demographic) to green practices is assessed. A Chi-square test, as the statistical tool, is used to test the variables. Sex, age, marital status, level of education, occupation and monthly income are the variables in the study to find out the association of them with green practices in tourism. Taken steps to test the variables clearly show that the association between green practices and monthly income is highly significant, meaning green practices by the tourists are acutely influenced by their income. The level of education creates significant differences in green practices by tourists. From the statistical test, it is evident that the association between green practices and the level of education is significant. It is surveyed from the analysis that tourists' sex, age, marital status, and occupation do not signify green practices in tourism. The formal statement, the association between green practices and other characteristics (sex, age, marital status, and occupation) of the tourists, is statistically tested and found to be insignificant.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Tourists are the final consumers of tourism who have a direct impact on the environment in the time of their travel around. Today, over the world awareness about environmental pollution is disseminated to the various stakeholders of the tourism industry. Day by day, tourists are becoming environmentally-friendly which, in the future, will lead to building a comfortable planet. They can contribute a lot to the environment through green practices. But in the question of awareness about green practice in tourism a large portion of the tourists doesn't know the issue. Again, among them, most of the tourists are confused about the possibility of green exercise in the time of traveling. Such practice heavily relies on tourists. Tourists' characteristics have a direct impact on this type of practice. The performed statistical tests have vivid evidence that several traits as sex, age, marital status, and occupation of the tourists have no significant association with green practices. On the other hand, the level of education and monthly income of the tourists are the two influential variables on green practices by them. The study proves that higher learned tourists confirm more green practices in tourism. Increased income by the tourists as well can motivate them to green practices. Tourists must come forward to protect the environment as much as possible through adopting green practices.

Limitation and Further Research

Centering on socioeconomic and demographic characteristics toward green practices in tourism, the study is ended. But this put emphasis on doesn't able to make available the fullest insight of the issue. Psychological characteristics of the tourists are also the vital role players in exercising green. So, in future, to explore more precise insights of this practice in tourism by the vacationers, the researchers have the chance to include the psychosomatic variables related to the behavior of the tourists. In further study perception, liking, preference, values and other psychological observable fact can be addressed.

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